

Representation of global mega-cities and their urban heat island in CORDEX-CORE regional climate model simulations

Gaby S. Langendijk¹, Jesus Fernandez², Matthias Demuzere³, Javier Diez-Sierra², Yaiza Quintana², Lluís Fita^{4,5,6}, Natalia Zazulie⁷, Rita Nogherotto^{7,8}, Andrea F. Carril^{4,5,6}, Kwok Pan Chun⁹, Tomas Halenka¹⁰, Peter Hoffmann¹¹, Luis E. Muñoz^{4,5,6}, Joni-Pekka Pietikäinen¹¹, Diana Rechid¹¹, Jiacan Yuan¹²

1. *Climate Adaptation and Disaster Risk Department, Deltares, PO Box 177, 2600 MH Delft, the Netherlands*
2. *Instituto de Física de Cantabria (IFCA), CSIC-Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain*
3. *B-Kode VOF, Ghent, Belgium*
4. *Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales (FCEN), Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA), Argentina*
5. *Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y la Atmósfera (CIMA/CONICET-UBA), Argentina*
6. *Instituto Franco-Argentino Para el Estudio del Clima y sus Impactos (IRL IFAECI/UBA-CONICET-CNRS-IRD), Argentina*
7. *The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste, Italy*
8. *The Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC), Italy*
9. *University of the West of England, UK*
10. *Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Atmospheric Physics, Prague, Czech Republic*
11. *Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS), Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Fischertwiete 1, 20095 Hamburg, Germany*
12. *Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences & Institute of Atmospheric Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai, China*

KEYWORDS

Urban heat island, urban land-use, regional climate modelling, CORDEX-CORE, global cities

31 Abstract

32

33 Cities are vulnerable to climate change, yet the interactions between urban and regional
34 climate remain insufficiently understood. This study assesses the capabilities of CORDEX-
35 CORE regional climate models in representing urban areas globally, focusing on land-surface
36 characteristics and urban heat island (UHI) evaluation. Despite their relatively coarse
37 resolution (~25 km), the two CORDEX-CORE models, REMO and RegCM, can capture urban
38 imprints of large cities. RegCM, with a single-layer urban canopy parameterization, represents
39 the UHI, especially at night. REMO tends to underestimate nighttime UHI due to its simple
40 bulk urban scheme. Across models, impervious surface areas are consistently
41 underestimated, with notable geographic imbalances across the world. Advancing regional
42 climate model simulations for cities requires both enhanced urban parameterizations, as well
43 as the integration of urban land-use data in the models. The findings support the next phase
44 of CMIP6 downscaling and enhance ongoing efforts in regional and urban climate modeling.

45

46

47 1. Introduction

48 Understanding the urban climate under ongoing and future climate change is pivotal for
49 planning adaptation actions to deal with and to minimize climate change impacts in cities.
50 Cities are hotspots of climate change impacts due to high population density, modified land
51 surfaces, and limited availability of vegetated areas ^{1,2}. Among these impacts, urban heat,
52 intensified by the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, poses a major risk to health, infrastructure,
53 and energy systems. The UHI effect, caused by increased impervious surfaces and reduced
54 vegetation, amplifies the severity of heatwaves beyond what is expected from climate change
55 alone ^{1,3,4}. In recognition of this critical role of urban areas in a changing climate, the
56 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has decided to include in the seventh
57 assessment cycle (AR7) a Special Report on Climate Change and Cities.

58

59 Currently, a large share of the urban climate change studies focus on one single-city or a few
60 cities at most and/or commonly employ one model ⁵⁻⁸. Often only shorter time periods are
61 assessed, for instance ranging from days, to months, up to one or two decades ⁹. In the short
62 time-scale studies, urban climate models are typically forced with climate change data or a
63 specific rate of climate change (e.g. 2 °C) is added to a historic extreme event (e.g. PGW
64 techniques ⁹). In addition, higher-resolution urban climate models center on the city-scale and
65 do not simulate interactions with global-to-regional climate change explicitly, particularly not in
66 a dynamic manner over longer timescales. Taking into account changes in the global and
67 regional climate is critical to understand the urban climate under climate change, as new
68 weather phenomena may arise in or near a particular city, or regional land-use might change
69 due to climatic changes around the city, which both can affect the urban climate ³.

70

71 Regional climate models (RCMs) offer a promising tool to provide future projections of urban
72 climates and their interactions with regional-to-global climate change, simultaneously allowing
73 for a comparison across cities in a region or continent ^{3,10,11}. Recently, numerous studies
74 showed that RCMs can simulate cities under climate change, particularly on the 0.11° spatial

75 resolution ¹², as well as on higher km-scale spatial resolutions ^{9,13}. Nevertheless, these studies
76 also point out that further improvements in the models would be required to improve the
77 representation of cities within RCMs ^{3,10}, particularly incorporating more sophisticated urban
78 schemes and underlying urban parameters to describe cities as input to the models. The
79 Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) Flagship Pilot Study on
80 the Urban environment and regional climate change (FPS URB-RCC,
81 https://ms.hereon.de/cordex_fps_urban) initiative is a global endeavour which aims to
82 understand the effect of urban areas on the regional climate, as well as the impact of regional
83 climate change on cities. This is done through new coordinated experiments with urbanized
84 RCMs, but also exploiting existing RCM output datasets ¹⁴. One of the key goals is to assess
85 multi-model uncertainty and understand the variability in the model representation of both
86 urban processes and city extent and characteristics.

87
88 Up to now, studies with RCMs focusing on urban areas are commonly centered around one
89 city, or a specific region ^{9,12,13,15}. The CORDEX Coordinated Output for Regional Evaluation
90 (CORDEX-CORE) activity offers a dataset covering almost all the land areas across the globe
91 by two RCMs on the ~25 km (0.22°) spatial resolution ¹⁶. In Europe EURO-CORDEX data at
92 ~12 km (0.11°) will also be used ¹⁷. Taking advantage of the evaluation simulations of this
93 global dataset driven by ERA-Interim reanalysis data ¹⁸, this work aims to understand the
94 capabilities of the CORDEX-CORE models to represent urban areas across the globe,
95 particularly focusing on the land-use descriptions and the urban heat island effect. The
96 analysis of these evaluation simulations provides the groundwork for using the CMIP5-driven
97 CORDEX-CORE ensemble for further urban climate change studies, and can inform future
98 regional climate modelling activities, such as the CORDEX-CMIP6 simulations, aiming at a
99 similar ~25 km horizontal resolution, and envisioned to provide new CORDEX-CORE global
100 coordinated output ¹⁹. An example of the impact of this study's outcomes is the application of
101 the proposed methodology in the urban layer of the C3S Atlas
102 (<https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu/atlas>), a live evolution of the IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas
103 (<https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch>), which provides climate change projections for a subset of the
104 cities analyzed in this work.

105
106 We present the key results divided into three main topics, a global city selection for RCMs at
107 ~25 km, an analysis of the land-use data, and an assessment of the urban heat island (UHI)
108 effect across cities using evaluation simulations. Thereafter the discussion follows. At the end
109 the data and methods used for this study are described, including an approach for a city
110 selection on the global scale that, in principle, could be captured by the CORDEX-CORE
111 horizontal resolution.

112
113 As a part of this study, the urban fraction data and the impervious fraction data of the
114 CORDEX-CORE dataset is published openly ²⁰ (see data availability section). These variables
115 are currently missing in public repositories and are key to enable further urban studies with
116 the CORDEX-CORE data.

118 2. Results

119 2.1 Underestimated urban land surface in regional climate 120 models

121 To evaluate the representation of urban land-surface in the CORDEX-CORE models, three
122 recent global high-resolution (urban) land cover datasets are selected, respectively the 10m
123 Esri land cover ²¹ (hereafter referred to as “ESRI”), the 10m ESA WorldCover land cover
124 dataset ²² (hereafter referred to as “ESA”), and the 100m global map of Local Climate Zones
125 ²³ (hereafter referred to as “LCZ”). For all the land cover datasets as well as for REMO and
126 RegCM the impervious surface area (ISA) is taken as the representation of urban areas, see
127 section 4.2.

128
129 The analysis of urban land use shows, first of all, that there are large disagreements between
130 global urban data products, confirming the findings of previous studies ²⁴. The ESRI product
131 consistently provides higher urban land cover fractions compared to ESA WorldCover, for all
132 CORDEX-CORE domains, with a maximum ISA fraction difference of 0.77 on the city-level
133 (Figure 1). The LCZ-based total ISA values are generally in between the ESRI and ESA
134 estimates, and are in line with the average of all three reference datasets combined, which is
135 hereafter named REF. As such, REF will serve as an ensemble estimate of ISA in forthcoming
136 analyses, and is assumed to average out the noise and uncertainties inherent to individual
137 datasets.

138

139
140 *Figure 1. Average ISA fraction per CORDEX-CORE domain, for LCZ, ESA, ESRI, REF,*
141 *REMO, RegCM, and CLMU. N refers to the number of the GHS-UCDB cities within the*
142 *domain. The yellow shaded area highlights the REF product against which the RCMs are*
143 *ultimately benchmarked. Note that, for EUR, the 0.11° spatial resolution was used.*

144

145 A comparison between RCMs’ ISA and REF for a total of 1741 cities within the Global Human
146 Settlement Urban Center Database ²⁵ (GHS-UCDB), reveals an overall strong underestimation
147 of the ISA in all models (Figure 1 and Supplementary Figure 1, and Supplementary Table 1).
148 On average, out of the 435.357 km² of surface area considered by the 1741 GHS-UCDB cities,
149 58% (252.990 km²) is impervious according to REF. For REMO and RegCM, this is only 17%

150 (44009 km²) and 6.8% (17356 km²), respectively. These biases are not geographically
151 uniform, but vary across CORDEX-CORE domains. For REMO, the largest domain-average
152 relative biases vary between -80 and -100% and can be found in CORDEX-CORE domains
153 at the ~25 km spatial resolution for Africa (AFR), Central America (CAM), South America
154 (SAM), East Asia (EAS), Southeast Asia (SEA) and South Asia (WAS). The cities in
155 Australasia (AUS), Europe (EUR) and North America (NAM) are slightly better represented,
156 with domain-average relative biases reduced to -60% (for EUR). RegCM applied a cut-off
157 value of 40% for its urban fraction data at the ~25 km spatial resolution (see section 4.1).
158 Therefore, all domains except EUR-11 have close to 0% urban fraction. For EUR-11 (~12 km),
159 the RegCM model has on average twice the amount of ISA compared to REMO, with
160 maximum values up to 60%, a value close to the REF average for this domain. The original
161 RegCM urban land-use component, so-called Community Land Model Urban^{8,26} (CLMU) (see
162 section 4.1), without cut-off value, consistently provides higher ISA values that are higher than
163 REMO for all domains except AUS and NAM. Nevertheless, also this “what if” scenario,
164 without the cut-off value, CLMU falls short compared to the REF estimates.

165

166 Besides the common ISA underestimation in the RCMs, also the intensity and size of the urban
167 representation differs: REMO has the highest maximum ISA values in domains AUS, EUR
168 and NAM, whilst most other domains have average maximum values below 0.1
169 (Supplementary Figure 2), surprisingly where some of the largest metropolitan areas exist.
170 The AUS, EUR and NAM domains are characterised by cities spanning up to six model grid
171 cells, whilst for the other domains, modelled cities are smaller with a maximum of 3 grid cells
172 with ISA greater than 0. Interestingly, when counting the number of pixels with ISA values
173 greater than 0.1, most cities disappear in REMO domains AFR, CAM, EAS, SAM, SEA, and
174 WAS, confirming that, if REMO presents impervious surfaces areas, they are rare and with
175 very low ISA values. CLMU generally shows higher maximum ISA values and a greater
176 number of urban pixels compared to RegCM. Unlike RegCM, CLMU is capable of assigning
177 non-zero ISA values across all CORDEX-CORE domains, including in underrepresented
178 regions such as AFR, CAM, SEA and WAS.

179

180 Using the IPCC AR6 reference regions²⁷, the relative ISA bias is visualised in greater detail
181 across global regions (Figure 2). In REMO, regions such as Northwestern North America
182 (NWM), Northern Europe (NEU), Southern (SAU), and Eastern Australia (EAU) show the
183 lowest relative biases (e.g., around -65% to -75%), while the majority of regions, particularly
184 in South and Central America, Sub-Saharan Africa, South and East Asia, and the Middle East,
185 exhibit very high negative biases (typically < -90%). RegCM displays uniformly high negative
186 biases across almost all regions, with many reaching -100%, indicating a near-complete
187 omission of urban land due to the use of the urban fraction cut-off. The CORDEX-CORE EUR
188 domain performs noticeably better, likely due to the use of the 0.11° (~12 km) model output
189 instead of the 0.22° (~25 km) resolution used for other domains. This finer resolution reduces
190 the number of cities excluded by the minimum urban fraction threshold, leading to a more
191 complete representation of impervious surfaces. CLMU shows a modestly improved
192 performance compared to REMO and RegCM, particularly in the European domains MED,
193 NEU, and WCE, in the African Sahara (SAH), and in parts of South and Southeast Asia (e.g.,
194 SAS, SEA, TIB), where relative biases range from approximately -57% to -75%. However,
195 large regions such as South America, Africa, and Oceania still show relative biases below -
196 80%, indicating persistent underrepresentation of impervious surfaces in those areas. Overall,

197 CLMU provides a relatively better urban land representation than REMO and RegCM but still
 198 underestimates urban ISA in most domains.
 199

200
 201 *Figure 2. Average relative ISA bias (%) per IPCC AR6 reference domain, for REMO (top*
 202 *panel), RegCM (middle panel) and CLMU (bottom panel). Data can be missing due to a lack*
 203 *of GHS-UCDB cities after selection or due to missing CORDEX-CORE simulations (e.g.*
 204 *Central-Asia domain). Please note that for EUR the 0.11° spatial resolution was used.*

205 2.2 Global city selection for regional climate modelling

206

207 A selection of cities was made for the evaluation of the UHI effect, based on a set of criteria
208 and associated methods suitable for regional climate model output datasets on the global
209 scale, as described in section 4.3. This city selection approach could be a blueprint for
210 upcoming global analyses on cities, particularly while using regional and potentially global
211 climate model output data. Given the relatively coarse resolution of CORDEX-CORE RCMs,
212 it is anticipated that the models will only represent larger urban areas.

213

214 An overview of the identified cities and their alignment with the selection criteria (see section
215 4.3) is shown in Figure 3, and supplementary Table 2 and 3, as well as supplementary Figure
216 3. The 41 selected cities, include 36 cities across the globe at the 0.22° spatial resolution,
217 which offer a balanced set of cities, in terms of: size (km² and population); climate zone;
218 geographic characteristics (mountain, in-land, coastal); and distributions across the globe. The
219 approximate number of grid points at 0.22° resolution (gp022) shows the potential of the city
220 to be represented by the relatively coarser spatial resolution of the CORDEX-CORE models
221 (see section 4.3). Cities with a gp022 below 0.9 were automatically excluded, as there would
222 be little chance that the RCMs would cover such cities with a minimum of one gridbox. For
223 analysing the added value of the 0.11° spatial resolution compared to 0.22° spatial resolution,
224 five additional cities were selected for Europe (Berlin, Naples, Athens, Barcelona, Prague). A
225 subset of 29 out of the total of 41 selected cities is also used in the urban layer of the C3S
226 Atlas (<https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu>).

227

228

229 *Figure 3. Location of cities with size above 0.9 gp022 (dots). Selected cities are highlighted in*
230 *red. Size of the dots represents the relative population. Background colors represent the*
231 *different Koppen-Geiger climate classification. Grey polygons delineate the boundaries of the*
232 *CORDEX domains.*

233

234

235 To complete the selection of cities for the UHI analysis, the identified cities are assessed for
236 actual representation within the CORDEX-CORE models. Figure 4 shows the number of grid
237 points for each of the 41 selected cities using five ISA thresholds: 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and

238 50% for both RegCM and REMO. The figure illustrates that using the higher ISA thresholds, 239 between 30% and 40% of the selected cities are not represented in either model. Using the 240 20% threshold, 75% of cities are represented, but in some cases, a single grid cell is remaining 241 to represent the city. This is especially evident with REMO, in which 16 of the selected cities 242 are represented by a single grid cell at the 20% threshold (e.g., Cairo, Johannesburg, Mexico 243 City, Beijing). It is worth noting that the cities of Luanda, Khartoum, Lagos, Chengdu, Manila, 244 Barcelona, and Dhaka disappear in both models at any threshold, while the cities of Istanbul, 245 Athens, Lima, and Shanghai are only detected by REMO at the 10% threshold.

246 The sensitivity analysis conducted for different ISA thresholds supports the determination of 247 the appropriate value for the ISA threshold for the CORDEX-CORE models at the 0.22° spatial 248 resolution (Figure 4). For ISA thresholds above 10%, most cities either disappeared or were 249 represented by only a single gridbox. Consequently, an ISA threshold of 10% was selected 250 for CORDEX-CORE, and this allows 80% of the initially selected cities to be distinguished at 251 least by REMO, as most of the cities are not captured by RegCM due to its 40% cut-off value. 252 For EUR-11, however, an ISA threshold of 40% was adopted, consistent with its higher 253 horizontal resolution. The selected thresholds are in line with previous studies, which typically 254 use urban fraction thresholds between 10% and 30% ^{12,28}. 255

256
257
258 *Figure 4. Number of grid cells considered as urban cells for different ISA thresholds (50, 40,*
259 *30, 20 and 10%) for RegCM (green) and REMO (orange). The left panel corresponds to*
260 *CORDEX-CORE (0.22°, ~25 km) and the right panel corresponds to EUR-11 (0.11°, ~12 km).*
261 *Black bars show the number of grid cells from the GHS-UCDB dataset.*

262
263 **2.3 Regional climate models can capture the urban heat island**

264 The urban heat island (UHI) effect as represented by both CORDEX-CORE models is 265 assessed for the selected cities, using the algorithm defined in Section 4.4 to classify urban 266 and surrounding areas. We consider the nocturnal UHI, as represented by the daily minimum 267 temperature (Figure 5), as well as the diurnal UHI, relying on maximum temperature (Figure

268 6). In both cases, we use as a reference the average temperature of the urban surroundings
269 and compute anomalies with respect to this reference for all grid cells. Thus, the anomaly in
270 the city surroundings averages to zero, and in the urban area averages to the mean UHI. That
271 is, a proxy of the mean temperature increase due to the presence of the city. Spatial maps
272 depict annual mean anomalies, while time series show the seasonal cycle of the UHI on a
273 monthly basis. We present New Delhi, Jakarta, Buenos Aires and Paris to show the variety in
274 the model results to depict the UHI effect.

275
276 New Delhi (Figure 5, top row) is represented by two REMO model grid cells (leftmost panel,
277 enclosed in red polygon) and by a single gridcell in RegCM (rightmost panel). The nocturnal
278 UHI effect for New Delhi cannot be discerned neither in the annual mean map, nor in the
279 annual cycle (second panel) by REMO, where the urban minimum temperature anomalies fall
280 within the envelope of the surrounding rural grid cells. A completely different picture emerges
281 from the RegCM simulation, which shows a strong urban signal, discernible both in the annual
282 mean and in the annual cycle (third panel), with UHI intensities above 2°C degrees in March
283 and April, and about 0.8°C degrees in July/August. This anomaly is clearly above the envelope
284 of that of the rural surrounding grid cells. Overall, the models seemingly underestimate the
285 UHI intensity, as observational studies for New Delhi show UHI intensities ranging between
286 0.8 and 6°C²⁹. The differing performance of the models in simulating the nocturnal UHI effect
287 is likely attributable to their different urban parameterization schemes. RegCM represents
288 urban canyons, which facilitate the retention of longwave radiation during nighttime. The
289 simplified rock surface in REMO has a lower thermal inertia and higher nocturnal radiative
290 cooling, leading to a more rapid dissipation of the heat accumulated during the daytime.

291
292 Figure 5 shows examples for several other cities. Jakarta (second row) is a coastal city and
293 shows a largely different extent across models (1 grid cell in REMO vs 4 in RegCM). The city
294 lies in the transition between the ocean grid cells with positive anomalies with respect to the
295 inland rural surroundings reference. This marine influence likely moderates the UHI effect.
296 Both models do show a UHI effect of 0.2 - 0.8°C, with RegCM depicting higher UHI intensities
297 than REMO. The UHI results from the RegCM model align better with previous observational
298 studies³⁰, which found UHI intensities between 1°C and 2.5°C for Jakarta. Buenos Aires (third
299 row, Figure _FIG_UHI_{tasmin}_) is also located by the large water body of the La Plata river.
300 However, in this case, RegCM shows a discernible nocturnal UHI, reaching about 1°C degree
301 in August. All RCMs underestimated the UHI, and only REMO is capable of reproducing the
302 maximum during summer³¹. Finally, we show an example of an inland city, Paris, at ~25 km
303 resolution (fourth row) and ~12 km resolution (fifth row). There is no RegCM simulation
304 available at ~25 km resolution but, in this case, the city shows a discernible nocturnal UHI also
305 for REMO, which is more profound at ~12 km resolution. The UHI effect is clearly noticeable
306 for RegCM at ~12 km resolution, reaching about 2.4°C degrees during the summer (June-
307 August).

308

309
 310 *Figure 5. Minimum temperature anomalies comparing urban areas (maroon polygon areas)*
 311 *with their vicinity (olive green polygonal areas) for New Delhi, Jakarta, Buenos Aires and Paris*
 312 *in different rows from top to bottom. The last row shows Paris at the ~12 km grid spacing used*
 313 *in EUR-11 simulations. Left panels correspond to the REMO model and right panels to*
 314 *RegCM. Spatial maps correspond to annual means, while the time series depict the monthly*
 315 *annual cycle of the urban grid-cells (enclosed in maroon polygons in the maps, shown as*
 316 *maroon time series; thick line representing the urban mean) and the surrounding areas (as*
 317 *olive green time series). Observational data at individual stations (only available over Paris)*
 318 *are shown as reference on the maps and as time series (urban stations in black and rural*
 319 *stations in green). For the observations, the urban/rural classification is done according to the*
 320 *GHS-UCDB polygons delimiting urban areas (in pink over the maps).*

321
 322 Unfortunately, observations are only available for Paris (Section 4.5) but, in any case, point
 323 observations cannot be straightforwardly compared to the model grid cell averages. The
 324 observed nocturnal UHI loosely resembles the model behaviour, with stronger summer UHI,
 325 reaching a value of about 2°C degrees, at least for the station closer to the city center.
 326

327 The situation for the diurnal UHI (Figure 6) differs notably, with the REMO model showing
 328 stronger intensities as compared to RegCM. During the day, the sea and urban anomalies
 329 have opposite signs, especially during the summer in extratropical areas, e.g. in Buenos Aires,
 330 where the urban area is now clearly discerned in REMO, reaching a 2°C degree intensity in
 331 summer (December-February) and missing its negative UHI in winter ³¹. The stronger diurnal
 332 UHI intensity simulated by REMO is also evident in Paris, particularly during summer and at
 333 ~12 km resolution. However, the magnitude of this UHI appears to be overestimated relative
 334 to observations. This bias is primarily attributable to the simplified bulk urban parameterization
 335 used in REMO, which tends to warm excessively the surface during daytime hours due to its
 336 limited representation of the city (no canyons or shadowing).

337
 338

339
 340 *Figure 6. As Figure _FIG_UHltasmin_, but for maximum temperature.*
 341

342
 343
 344

345 The UHI intensity for all selected cities is summarized in Figure 7. If available in the Global
346 Historical Climatology Network daily (GHCNd) observational dataset, the observed UHI is
347 shown (see section 4.5). The summary figure shows, generally, the behaviour that we have
348 illustrated in the examples in Figures 5 and 6. Coastal cities tend to show stronger nocturnal
349 UHI intensities in REMO, but this is likely mixed with the marine influence over coastal grid
350 cells in general, as compared to the reference rural grid cells, which lie further inland. A notable
351 reversal in this behaviour is shown in Los Angeles, with cooler summer (June-August)
352 temperatures in the city than in the inland surroundings. This could be due to the summer
353 upwelling in the area. This qualitative behaviour also appears in the observations. REMO
354 tends to show milder nocturnal UHI than RegCM, but stronger diurnal UHIs, especially in
355 summer. Cities at high elevation or in complex terrain show different behaviour as the selection
356 of surrounding areas becomes more challenging; typically, many surrounding grid cells need
357 to be excluded by the height difference and the city lies above the surroundings in the model
358 (e.g. Mexico City), partly compensating for the UHI effect. Cities in deserted areas also show
359 different behaviour. As the surrounding areas of these cities are barren and barely vegetated,
360 the land is heated up very quickly during the day time. As there is more green infrastructure,
361 cities tend to have lower temperature than the surroundings during the day time³². The higher
362 resolution (EUR-11 vs EUR-22) leads to stronger UHI intensities, especially in summer. The
363 only exception is Athens, where the surrounding sea mask leads to largely different reference
364 rural grid cell areas (not shown).
365 We also looked into the potential impact of urban areas in the 3-dimensional atmospheric
366 circulation. Such impacts could make CORDEX-CORE models also relevant for studies such
367 as: impact to land-sea breezes, storm propagation, thermal inversions, air-quality
368 assessments. However, the results (not shown) did not show any significant impact in the
369 atmosphere. The limited vertical resolution in the available CORDEX-CORE output data made
370 the analysis challenging. A higher spatial resolution and more complex urban schemes could
371 lead to such effects, especially through the interaction of convection and the urban plume^{33,34}.

372
373
374
375
376
377
378
379
380
381
382
383
384

395 3. Discussion

396

397 The CORDEX-CORE dataset provides regional climate model simulations with a relatively
398 high spatial resolution of ~ 25 km (0.22°), which will become standard in the upcoming
399 CORDEX-CMIP6 data set. The CORDEX-CORE dataset consists of two models in which
400 cities are represented via a bulk approach (REMO) or an urban parameterization (RegCM, for
401 most domains). Unfortunately, two of the domains with the largest megacities (NAM and EAS)
402 did not include a city representation in RegCM. In the rest of the domains, only a few
403 megacities are represented in this model, due to a cut-off value of 40% used for the impervious
404 surface area fraction. Despite these clear limitations of the existing CORDEX-CORE data set,
405 we show which megacities are actually represented in the models and how the cities affect
406 minimum and maximum temperatures for the urban areas and its surroundings. Assessing the
407 evaluation simulations for the UHI we find that the bulk approach used in REMO leads to
408 stronger daytime UHI, while an urban parameterization in RegCM develops a stronger and
409 somewhat more realistic nighttime UHI, as well as more realistic UHI intensity for those cities
410 for which observations or literature were available, although the lack of proper observations
411 makes it difficult to draw robust conclusions. Over Europe, we show how the increased spatial
412 resolution leads to more realistic UHI effects.

413

414 In addition, our results show that the urban land cover is strongly underestimated in both
415 REMO and RegCM compared to other reference land surface datasets, and these biases vary
416 across geographic regions. In addition, the nature of the urban description tends to be
417 different, with overall highest ISA values and more urbanised pixels in REMO compared to
418 RegCM, which applied a cut-off threshold for ISA that removed most urban areas; however,
419 using CLMU's native database without such a threshold - as in the CLMU scenario- would
420 significantly improve the representation of cities in RegCM.

421

422 All these results are promising regarding the upcoming CORDEX-CMIP6 dataset ¹⁹, where
423 many of the RCMs are urbanized and will produce simulations at the horizontal resolutions
424 considered in this work (~ 25 and ~ 12 km). A straightforward extension of this work will be
425 possible when the CORDEX-CMIP6 evaluation simulations become available, as these will
426 likely cover more of our mega-cities selection and in a more realistic way. In a follow up study,
427 further use of local observations could improve the evaluation of the UHI, as well as a more
428 in-depth comparison between cities across domains, climate zones and geographic
429 characteristics could be made. To enable further studies, we publish openly the missing urban
430 fraction-related datasets corresponding to the existing CORDEX-CORE simulations, which
431 were collected for this work. The urban layer of the C3S Atlas
432 (<https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu>) builds on these results by providing future climate
433 projections for several temperature-related indices and is expected to expand its coverage to
434 include more cities and indices using the upcoming CORDEX-CMIP6 models.

435

436 Aside from the improvements related to higher resolution, there are two critical areas for
437 further improvements resulting from our study that could greatly benefit the representation of
438 cities in regional climate models, and therefore the accurate simulation of cities and their
439 interactions with regional climate change. Firstly, regional climate models need to incorporate

440 or improve their urban parameterizations and, secondly, these urban parameterizations
441 require accurate urban land cover datasets as input.

442

443 With respect to improving urban parameterizations in RCMs, large-scale international urban
444 model comparison experiments indicate that dozens of urban parameterizations exist ³⁵⁻³⁹.
445 These schemes differ widely in complexity, the physical processes they represent, and the
446 quality of their outputs, a diversity that is considered a strength, not a weakness. As shown in
447 the Urban-PLUMBER project ³⁹, even relatively simple models can produce skillful energy flux
448 estimates, particularly when coupled with robust hydrological and vegetation schemes. More
449 complex schemes, while theoretically offering greater process realism, do not consistently
450 outperform simpler ones, often because their representation of hydrology and vegetation is
451 less developed, diminishing their overall effectiveness ³⁹. Crucially, the point is not to choose
452 the "best" scheme, but to recognize that urban parameterizations are becoming essential, and
453 no longer negligible at higher spatial resolutions ^{3,14,40}. Modeling centers must therefore
454 commit to explicitly representing cities in their systems.

455

456 The explicit representation of urban land cover in RCMs to accurately simulate the complex
457 interactions between cities and the regional climate depends on accurate urban land cover
458 data and associated physical and morphological parameters. As pointed out by different works
459 ^{5,23,41}, cities are often underrepresented in climate models due to an underutilization of recent
460 and emerging global datasets describing their form and function - factors critical for modeling
461 e.g. energy fluxes, heat retention, and pollutant dispersion. Responding to this gap, Ching et
462 al. ⁴² and collaborators established the World Urban Database and Access Portal Tools
463 (WUDAPT) initiative and produced a global map of Local Climate Zones ²³ that provides a
464 standardized global urban typology, linked to meaningful urban canopy parameters, in a
465 language most urban parameterizations understand. This approach was adopted by a range
466 of (regional) modeling systems: for example, the Weather Research and Forecasting model
467 (WRF) ^{43,44}, the ICON and COSMO-CLM model systems ^{45,46}, and ALARO-SURFEX ⁴⁷. In
468 addition, an increasing number of spatially explicit urban land cover and morphology data sets
469 become available ^{24,48}, offering greater detail on building footprints, heights, impervious
470 surfaces, and more. Notable recent developments include the U-Surf ⁴⁹ and the GloUCP ⁵⁰
471 datasets tailored for CESM and WRF respectively, both providing globally consistent, spatially
472 continuous data at 1 km resolution. These datasets are specifically designed to support
473 kilometer-scale urban-resolving global and regional Earth system modeling and represent a
474 major step forward in improving the realism of urban climate simulations at the global scale.
475 The challenge now lies not in the availability of appropriate, fit-for-scale urban data, but in
476 effectively integrating these diverse and often high-resolution sources into RCMs in a scalable,
477 consistent, and climate-relevant manner - a process still hindered by mismatches between
478 data structures and model requirements, lack of standardization, and limited operational
479 workflows ⁴⁰.

480

481

482

483

484 4. Methods

485 4.1 CORDEX-CORE dataset

486 The CORDEX-CORE EXP-I dataset consists of two regional climate models, RegCM4 and
487 REMO2015, downscaling three CMIP5 global climate models to the approximate ~25 km
488 (0.22°) spatial resolution. The simulations cover almost all land areas of the world using nine
489 domains, for two greenhouse gas representative concentration pathways ⁵¹ (RCP2.6 and
490 RCP8.5). The dataset provides ERA-Interim driven evaluation simulations between 1979–
491 2017, as well as climate projections from 2006–2100, with a reference historical time period
492 from 1971–2005 ^{52–54}. Further information about the CORDEX-CORE experiment is provided
493 in Giorgi et al. ⁵². This study uses the ERA-interim driven evaluation simulations ⁵³ for the
494 analysis of the UHI. Nine CORDEX-CORE domains are simulated by the CORDEX-CORE
495 RCMs (Figure 3): Africa (AFR-22), Central America (CAM-22), South America (SAM-22), East
496 Asia (EAS-22), Southeast Asia (SEA-22), South Asia (WAS-22), North America (NAM-22),
497 Australia (AUS-22), and Europe (EUR-22 for REMO, and EUR-11 for both REMO and
498 RegCM).

499
500 The regional climate models RegCM and REMO represent urban areas differently. To enable
501 a comparison, we use the impervious surface area (ISA) as a common metric, as "urban
502 fraction" is inconsistently defined across models and not available for REMO. RegCM uses
503 the Community Land Model (CLM) as land-surface scheme ²⁶, that represents spatial land
504 surface heterogeneity via five landunit types: vegetated, lake, glacier, crop and urban. The
505 latter unit is treated by the CLM Urban (CLMU) model, a single-layer urban canopy model in
506 which the urban fraction is further decomposed into three classes ⁸: the tall building district
507 (TBD), and high density (HD), and medium density (MD) classes. TBD is defined as an area
508 of at least 1 km² with buildings greater than or equal to ten stories tall, with a small pervious
509 fraction (5-15% of plan area). The HD class can encompass commercial, residential, or
510 industrial areas that are characterised by buildings three to ten stories tall with a pervious
511 fraction typically in the range of 5-25%. The MD class is usually characterised by row houses
512 or apartment complexes one to three stories tall with a pervious fraction of 20-60%. For each
513 of these classes, urban morphology characteristics such as fraction of pervious surface (e.g.,
514 vegetation), roof area, and impervious surfaces (e.g., roads and sidewalks) are defined for 33
515 regions according to Jackson et al. ⁵⁵. For more information, see the work by Oleson and
516 Feddema ⁸, or Figure A7 in Lipson et al. ³⁹.

517
518 In order to obtain the total impervious surface area for each model gridcell, the roof fraction
519 and the impervious road fraction are summed and scaled with the percentage urban for each
520 density class. Summing over all density classes then provides the total impervious surface
521 area. Note however that for most RegCM simulation domains, a cut-off value of 40% is used
522 for the urban fraction, removing most of the cities in most domains. An exception is the EUR-
523 11 domain, where no cut-off value is used. Additionally, over NAM and EAS, no urban areas
524 were considered. Understanding this heterogeneity in the urban representation in RegCM is
525 key to users of this dataset for urban analyses. For the sake of clarity, the original urban
526 surface data available for CLMU is also processed with the Toolbox for Human-Earth System
527 Integration & Scaling (THESIS) tool (see Section 5 in ⁸ for more details), and benchmarked
528 against the reference ISA datasets.

529
530 The REMO version used in this work (REMO2015) utilizes three fractional sub-grid tiles: land,
531 water and ice ^{56,57}. The land tile characteristics are represented through land surface
532 parameters, such as snow-free surface albedo, roughness length, leaf-area index, forest and
533 vegetation fraction, and soil water holding capacity. These parameters are derived from ^{58,59}
534 and are allocated from more than seventy Land Use / Land Cover (LULC) types, including
535 urban surfaces. The sub-tile (land) fractions of these parameters are based on the 1-km
536 resolution Global Land Cover Characterization (GLCC) dataset Version 2, primarily derived
537 from 1992 to 1993 Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data ⁶⁰. The GLCC
538 data is constructed by the U.S. Geological Survey ⁶¹ and by using the fractions it provides, the
539 land surface parameters of the impervious, bare soil and vegetated fractions are aggregated,
540 weighted by their respective LULC fraction. The fraction of the purely sealed/impervious
541 surfaces of urban areas are represented as a rock surface, which is described in the model
542 by a relatively high roughness length, high albedo, zero vegetation cover and no water storage
543 capacities ^{12,54,58}. More details on how REMO utilizes the fractional tiles in the climate
544 simulations, including land characteristics, can be found from Pietikäinen et al. ⁶².

545 4.2 Urban land surface representation in models

546
547 Based on the recent work by Chakraborty et al. ²⁴, that identified large disagreements between
548 global urban data products across spatiotemporal scales, three recent global high-resolution
549 (urban) land cover datasets are selected to evaluate the ISA representation of impervious
550 surface areas in the REMO and RegCM models. First, the 10m Esri land cover (hereafter
551 referred to as “ESRI”) presents the product with the highest urban land (built area) percentage,
552 being described as “*Human-made structures; major road and rail networks; large homogenous*
553 *impervious surfaces, including parking structures, office buildings and residential housing*” ²¹.
554 Second, the 10m ESA WorldCover land cover dataset (hereafter referred to as “ESA”) has
555 one of the lowest urban land percentages, and defines built-up areas as “*Buildings, roads and*
556 *other man-made structures such as railroads. Buildings include both residential and industrial*
557 *buildings. Urban green (parks, sport facilities) is not included in this class*” ²². Third, also the
558 100m global map of Local Climate Zones ²³ is used (hereafter referred to as “LCZ”), as it is
559 designed as a globally consistent and climate-relevant dataset of urban parameters that is
560 increasingly used in a variety of climate models, including WRF ^{43,63}, COSMO-CLM ^{46,64}, and
561 CESM ⁶⁵. Here, the seventeen Local Climate Zones labels are converted to total ISA
562 impervious surface area that is calculated as the sum of the outer ranges of the building plan
563 area (building footprints) and impervious plan area (paved, rock), according to Table 3 in
564 Stewart and Oke (2012) ⁶⁶.

565
566 The representation of the urban land, including the urban and impervious fractions, in the
567 RCMs is evaluated for a total of 1741 Global Human Settlement Urban Center Database
568 (GHS-UCDB) cities ²⁵, representing a total population of 2.14 billion people, which is 65% of
569 the total population represented by the GHS-UCDB (accounting for UCD cities with quality flag
570 1). The selected cities (Supplementary Table 1) are selected based on their area (> 62.5 km²),
571 and are each assigned to a corresponding CORDEX-CORE domain via the IPCC AR6
572 reference regions ⁶⁷. For cities that span two IPCC AR6 reference regions, the IPCC AR6 label
573 is assigned based on the domain containing the largest portion of the city. For RegCM, the

574 representation of the urban land is evaluated as used in CORDEX-CORE (simulations with a
 575 40% cut-off threshold in many domains) retaining only urban fractions above 40%, as well as
 576 using the latest default CLMU urban properties dataset that is processed using the official
 577 THESIS (Toolbox for Human-Earth System Integration & Scaling) tool ⁸, with a cut-off value of
 578 1%. CLMU thus presents a 'what-if' scenario for all domains except EUR, demonstrating the
 579 full potential of RegCM -or any global or regional climate model using the Community Land
 580 Model as its land surface scheme- to more accurately represent global urban land cover by
 581 incorporating the latest CLMU urban dataset.

582
 583 For each selected city (Supplementary Table 1), the impervious surface fraction prescribed in
 584 the models is compared to values obtained from individual global urban datasets (ESA, ESRI,
 585 and LCZ) and their average, hereafter referred to as REF. This comparison is made on the
 586 city-level, by averaging all pixels within the GHS-UCDB polygon. The coarse-resolution
 587 CORDEX models on a curvilinear grid are first reprojected onto a regular grid using nearest-
 588 neighbor interpolation, followed by an area-weighted averaging method that considers partial
 589 pixel values. Figure 8 provides an example of all ISA datasets and their corresponding average
 590 ISA value for New Delhi, India. In addition to the average ISA, the maximum ISA value as well
 591 as the number of pixels that have an ISA value greater than 0 and 0.1 are retrieved, based on
 592 all pixels that touch the GHS-UCDB polygon.

593

594
 595 *Figure 8. Illustration of the impervious surface area for Delhi (India), for the ESA, ESRI, and*
 596 *LCZ reference products, REF (as the average of ESA, ESRI, and LCZ), and the two RCMs*
 597 *REMO and RegCM (with a cut-off value of >0.4 for urban fraction). CLMU refers to the urban*
 598 *fraction that RegCM would have recognized if the 0.4 threshold for the urban fraction had not*
 599 *been applied. The outline of the GHS-UCDB polygon for Delhi is shown in white. The values*
 600 *in brackets denote the mean ISA for the polygon.*

601

602 4.3 Global city selection approach

603

604 A structured approach was developed to select cities across the globe for the evaluation of
 605 the UHI effect using the CORDEX-CORE dataset. A set of criteria and associated methods to
 606 comply with these criteria were identified. Besides the size of the urban area in km², also its
 607 population is considered, as the latter is particularly relevant in terms of impacts felt by people.
 608 In addition, we aimed to cover cities in different geographic settings as well as climate zones,
 609 and sought a global balance across CORDEX domains. Furthermore, we considered climate
 610 impacts and the availability of observations. Finally, seven key criteria and associated
 611 methods were employed to select the cities, which are summarized in
 612 Table 1.

613

614 *Table 1. Key criteria guiding the global city selection for regional climate model datasets.*

Criteria	Method	Dataset link or reference
Area size	A rough estimate was defined of the amount of CORDEX-CORE (0.22°) grid points (so-called gp022) occupied by the urban centre, by considering its area (km ²) in the GHS-UCDB divided by 600 km ² (an intermediate value between the REMO and RegCM grid cell sizes). The selected cities have a minimum gp022 of 0.9, to represent cities with at least one gridbox (except for Europe 0.11 analysis, smaller cities included). This “ <i>a priori</i> ” estimate of the city size can be compared with the actual urban extent represented by each model.	Giorgi et al. (2021) Teichmann et al. (2021) Remedio et al. (2019) Florczyk et al. (2019)
Population size	The Global Human Settlement Urban Center Database (GHS-UCDB) of cities 2015 was used for population size, containing information for more than 10,000 Urban Centres, regarding city location and extent, and providing a set of geographical, socio-economic and environmental attributes.	Florczyk et al. (2019) <i>While this study uses the GHS-UCDB 2019 version, we acknowledge that a more recent release of GHS-UCDB is available⁶⁸ that may be integrated in future versions of this work.</i>
Geography	Three different geographic characteristics were considered: coastal; inland; mountains. The city location and elevation from the GHS-UCDB was used to classify the geographical setting of each city.	Florczyk et al. (2019)
Climate zones	The Köppen-Geiger classification was used to define the climate zone of the cities. We relied on the existing, openly-available global classification by Chen and Chen (2013), using long-term climate data (1901-2010) at half-degree resolution. Each city was assigned the climate classification of the grid point nearest to the GHS-UCDB urban centre.	Chen and Chen (2013) Florczyk et al. (2019)
Global balance	In line with the global cover of the CORDEX-CORE dataset, a set of cities covering all CORDEX domains was aimed for. A balance was sought between CORDEX domains that tend to have larger cities than others. A CORDEX domain was automatically assigned to the cities via their corresponding IPCC AR6 region.	Diez-Sierra et al. (2022)

Climate impact	Smaller or less populated cities might still be subject to substantial climate risks, or vulnerabilities. This aspect was handled in combination with the city size and global balance to fill gaps in domains.	
Observations availability	At this stage, the availability of observations in the urban and surrounding areas was not a defining factor for city selection, as obtaining observations for cities and their direct surroundings remains a challenge at the global scale. In our study, the search for observations was inverted. We first selected the cities following the above criteria and then used the Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) database as observational reference for those cities where observations of this network are available (section 4.5).	Menne et al. (2012)

615

616 4.4 Differentiating urban areas and its surroundings

617

618 Delineating urban areas from their surrounding rural environments presents a significant
619 challenge for RCMs, primarily due to their relatively coarse spatial resolution and the diverse
620 land surface representations they employ. Although administrative city boundaries are
621 available, they cannot be directly applied to the model data, as the urban land cover defined
622 by each RCM often diverges substantially from these official boundaries. To resolve this, we
623 adopt a land cover–based method to classify grid cells as either urban or rural, identifying
624 cities as clusters of urban land cover according to each model's internal representation.
625 However, the relatively low resolution of the CORDEX-CORE ensemble adds further
626 complexity to this classification.

627

628 Following previous work on delineating rural surrounding areas^{12,13,28,69–74}, an algorithm was
629 developed specifically for application to RCMs⁷⁵. This method is based on the following
630 criteria: (1) potential urban surrounding areas are defined as grid cells with ISA values below
631 10%; (2) large water bodies –defined as areas with more than 30% water coverage fraction–
632 are excluded; and (3) grid cells with elevation differences greater than 100 meters relative to
633 the urban area are also excluded. The grid cells that meet these criteria are selected as the
634 surroundings of a city through an iterative process using a morphological dilation function
635 applied to the urban cells, while maintaining a ratio 1:2 between the number of urban and non-
636 urban surrounding grid cells, in line with previous studies⁷⁶. A detailed description of the
637 algorithm used to delineate urban and rural surrounding areas is available in Diez-Sierra et al.
638⁷⁵. All the above mentioned parameters can be modified, leading to different urban-rural areas.
639 The selection above is the result of sensitivity analyses which were conducted to refine the
640 selection criteria for urban grid cells (Figure 4) and to improve the accuracy of distinguishing
641 urban areas from their rural surroundings. Figure 9 shows an example of the selected urban
642 and rural surroundings areas for the cities of Buenos Aires (0.22° resolution) and Paris (0.11°).
643

644
 645 *Figure 9. Examples of urban and vicinity masks for Buenos Aires (top panels) and Paris*
 646 *(bottom) in both models (in columns). Cells with red and olive borders represent urban and*
 647 *non-urban (rural) surrounding areas, respectively. Rural cells are selected iteratively through*
 648 *a morphological dilation ensuring a minimum ratio (in this case, 2) between the number of*
 649 *urban and rural cells. The algorithm excludes large water bodies (land fraction below 70%)*
 650 *and areas with a large difference (>100m) in model elevation with respect to the urban area*
 651 *elevation range.*
 652

653 4.5 Global in-situ observations for UHI evaluation

654 The CORDEX-CORE analysis about the urban heat island effect is assessing the model
 655 output data with observations for cities and their direct surroundings, for those cities where
 656 observations are available. This is only as a qualitative reference, since point observations
 657 cannot be straightforwardly compared to the model grid cell averages. We classified the
 658 observational stations as urban or rural according to the GHS-UCDB polygons delimiting
 659 urban center areas. We used two sources of in-situ observations. The first is the Global
 660 Historical Climatology Network daily (GHCNd) ⁷⁷. The GHCNd is an integrated database of
 661 daily climate summaries from land surface stations across the globe. GHCNd is made up of
 662 daily climate records from numerous sources that have been integrated and subjected to a
 663 common suite of quality assurance reviews. The GHCNd contains records from more than
 664 100,000 stations in 180 countries and territories. It provides numerous daily variables,
 665 including maximum and minimum temperature, total daily precipitation, snowfall, and snow

666 depth. Both record length and period of record vary by station and cover intervals ranging from
667 less than a year to more than 175 years. For the evaluation of the urban heat island effect
668 (Section 2.3), the minimum and maximum temperatures observational records were used.

669

670 In addition to GHCNd data, we used data from MétéoFrance for the city of Paris, the main
671 demonstrator city in the FPS URB-RCC. These data correspond to ten weather stations
672 covering the period 1980-2017 with hourly resolution and a ratio of missing values below 30%
673 for each of the stations. Seven of the stations are located in the urban area and three are in
674 cropland areas.

675

676

677

678

679

680 Data availability

681 CORDEX-CORE and EURO-CORDEX data for daily maximum and minimum near surface
682 temperature, orography, and land area fraction are publicly available through ESGF
683 (<https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cordex-dkrz/>).

684 Urban and impervious surface area fractions were collected and post-processed as part of
685 this work and have been made publicly available on Zenodo ²⁰
686

687 Code availability

688 The Python code for city selection, impervious surface fraction calculation and related tasks
689 is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/FPS-URB-RCC/CORDEX-CORE-WG>).

690 The Python code for the urban heat island analysis is also available on GitHub
691 (<https://github.com/FPS-URB-RCC/urclimask>).

692

693

694 Acknowledgements

695 We would like to thank the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and the COordinated
696 Regional climate Downscaling EXperiment (CORDEX) for their endorsement and support to the
697 CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study URB-RCC. We wish to thank the partners of the WCRP CORDEX FPS
698 URB-RCC for their engagement and contributions to the initiative. M. D. is supported by the European
699 Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101137851, project
700 CARMINE (Climate-Resilient Development Pathways in Metropolitan Regions of Europe,
701 <https://www.carmine-project.eu/>). DR acknowledges support from the European Union's HORIZON
702 project FOCAL - Efficient Exploration of Climate Data Locally - under grant agreement
703 No.101137787. J.F. acknowledges support from the European Union's HORIZON Research and
704 Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101081555, project IMPETUS4CHANGE. G.S.L. and
705 J.F. acknowledge support from project PROTECT (PID2023-149997OA-I00), funded by
706 MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU. T.H. acknowledges support from the
707 European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No
708 101081555, project IMPETUS4CHANGE and by the Johannes Amos Comenius Programme (OP
709 JAC) project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004605, Natural and anthropogenic georisk.

710 Author contributions

711 G.S.L., T.H. and P.H. initiated the study as part of the CORDEX FPS URB-RCC proposal. G.S.L.,
712 J.F., M.D., J.D-S. developed the conceptual approach together with the co-authors. M.D. conducted
713 the land-use analysis. J.F., J.D-S. Y.Q. and G.S.L. conducted the urban heat island analysis. G.S.L.,
714 J.F., M.D., J.D-S., L.F., N.Z., R.N., K.P.C., T.H., J.Y., P.H., J-P.K., developed the city selection
715 approach and G.S.L., J.F., J.D-S., L.F., N.Z., R.N., J-P.K. conducted the associated analysis. G.S.L.,
716 J.F., M.D., J.D-S. took the lead on writing the manuscript. All authors contributed to writing and
717 revising the manuscript.

718 Competing interests

719 No competing interests to declare.

720 References

- 721 1. Dodman, D. *et al.* Cities, Settlements and Key Infrastructure. in *Climate Change 2022: Impacts,*
722 *Adaptation and Vulnerability. Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of*
723 *the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S.*
724 *Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem,*
725 *B. Rama (eds.)]* 907–1040 (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY,
726 USA, 2022). doi:10.1017/9781009325844.
- 727 2. UN Habitat. *Guiding Principles for City Climate Action Planning.* 40 [https://unhabitat.org/guiding-](https://unhabitat.org/guiding-principles-for-city-climate-action-planning)
728 [principles-for-city-climate-action-planning](https://unhabitat.org/guiding-principles-for-city-climate-action-planning) (2015).
- 729 3. Masson, V., Lemonsu, A., Hidalgo, J. & Voogt, J. Urban Climates and Climate Change. *Annu.*
730 *Rev. Environ. Resour.* **45**, 411–444 (2020).
- 731 4. Oke, T. R., Mills, G., Christen, A. & Voogt, J. A. *Urban Climates.* (Cambridge University Press,
732 2017). doi:10.1017/9781139016476.
- 733 5. Hertwig, D., Ng, M., Grimmond, S., Vidale, P. L. & McGuire, P. C. High-resolution global climate
734 simulations: Representation of cities. *Int. J. Climatol.* **41**, 3266–3285 (2021).
- 735 6. Katzfey, J., Schlünzen, H., Hoffmann, P. & Thatcher, M. How an urban parameterization affects a
736 high-resolution global climate simulation. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **146**, 3808–3829 (2020).
- 737 7. Katzfey, J., Schlünzen, K. H. & Hoffmann, P. Effects of urban areas on the diurnal cycle of
738 temperature and precipitation in a global climate simulation. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **150**, 4885–
739 4914 (2024).
- 740 8. Oleson, K. W. & Feddema, J. Parameterization and Surface Data Improvements and New
741 Capabilities for the Community Land Model Urban (CLMU). *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.* **12**,
742 e2018MS001586 (2020).
- 743 9. Argüeso, D., Evans, J. P., Fita, L. & Bormann, K. J. Temperature response to future urbanization
744 and climate change. *Clim. Dyn.* **42**, 2183–2199 (2014).
- 745 10. Hamdi, R. *et al.* The State-of-the-Art of Urban Climate Change Modeling and Observations. *Earth*
746 *Syst. Environ.* **4**, 631–646 (2020).
- 747 11. Nazarian, N. *et al.* Integration of urban climate research within the global climate change
748 discourse. *PLOS Clim.* **3**, e0000473 (2024).
- 749 12. Langendijk, G. S., Rechid, D. & Jacob, D. Urban Areas and Urban–Rural Contrasts under Climate
750 Change: What Does the EURO-CORDEX Ensemble Tell Us?—Investigating near Surface
751 Humidity in Berlin and Its Surroundings. *Atmosphere* **10**, 730 (2019).
- 752 13. Langendijk, G. S., Rechid, D., Sieck, K. & Jacob, D. Added value of convection-permitting
753 simulations for understanding future urban humidity extremes: case studies for Berlin and its
754 surroundings. *Weather Clim. Extrem.* **33**, 100367 (2021).
- 755 14. Langendijk, G. S. *et al.* Towards better understanding the urban environment and its interactions
756 with regional climate change - The WCRP CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study URB-RCC. *Urban Clim.*
757 **58**, 102165 (2024).
- 758 15. Michau, Y., Lemonsu, A., Lucas-Picher, P., Schneider, M. & Caillaud, C. On the future evolution
759 of heatwaves in French cities and associated rural areas: Insights from a convection-permitting
760 model. *Urban Clim.* **55**, 101920 (2024).
- 761 16. Giorgi, F. *et al.* The CORDEX-CORE EXP-I Initiative: Description and Highlight Results from the
762 Initial Analysis. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **103**, E293–E310 (2022).
- 763 17. Jacob, D. *et al.* Regional climate downscaling over Europe: perspectives from the EURO-
764 CORDEX community. *Reg. Environ. Change* **20**, 51 (2020).

- 765 18. Dee, D. P. *et al.* The ERA-Interim reanalysis: configuration and performance of the data
766 assimilation system. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **137**, 553–597 (2011).
- 767 19. CORDEX. CORDEX experiment design for dynamical downscaling of CMIP6. (2025)
768 doi:10.5281/ZENODO.15199301.
- 769 20. Langendijk, G. S. *et al.* CORDEX-CORE urban and impervious surface area dataset (1.0.0).
770 Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15700267> (2025).
- 771 21. Karra, K. *et al.* Global land use / land cover with Sentinel 2 and deep learning. in *2021 IEEE*
772 *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium IGARSS 4704–4707* (IEEE, Brussels,
773 Belgium, 2021). doi:10.1109/IGARSS47720.2021.9553499.
- 774 22. Zanaga, D. *et al.* ESA WorldCover 10 m 2020 v100. [object Object]
775 <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5571936> (2021).
- 776 23. Demuzere, M. *et al.* A global map of local climate zones to support earth system modelling and
777 urban-scale environmental science. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **14**, 3835–3873 (2022).
- 778 24. Chakraborty, T. *et al.* Large disagreements in estimates of urban land across scales and their
779 implications. *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 9165 (2024).
- 780 25. Florczyk, A. *et al.* GHS-UCDB R2019A - GHS Urban Centre Database 2015, multitemporal and
781 multidimensional attributes. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC)
782 <https://doi.org/10.2905/53473144-B88C-44BC-B4A3-4583ED1F547E> (2019).
- 783 26. Lawrence, D. M. *et al.* The Community Land Model Version 5: Description of New Features,
784 Benchmarking, and Impact of Forcing Uncertainty. *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.* **11**, 4245–4287
785 (2019).
- 786 27. Iturbide, M. *et al.* An update of IPCC climate reference regions for subcontinental analysis of
787 climate model data: definition and aggregated datasets. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **12**, 2959–2970
788 (2020).
- 789 28. Daniel, M. *et al.* Benefits of explicit urban parameterization in regional climate modeling to study
790 climate and city interactions. *Clim. Dyn.* **52**, 2745–2764 (2019).
- 791 29. Mohan, M. *et al.* Assessment of urban heat island intensities over Delhi. in 4 (Yokohama, Japan,
792 2009).
- 793 30. Siswanto, S. *et al.* Spatio-temporal characteristics of urban heat Island of Jakarta metropolitan.
794 *Remote Sens. Appl. Soc. Environ.* **32**, 101062 (2023).
- 795 31. Lozada, M. & Camilloni, I. Variabilidad espacio-temporal de la isla de calor superficial en tres
796 ciudades argentinas. *Meteorologica* **47**, e012–e012 (2022).
- 797 32. Rajeswari, J. R. *et al.* Urban heat island phenomenon in a desert, coastal city: The impact of
798 urbanization. *Urban Clim.* **56**, 102016 (2024).
- 799 33. Freitag, B. M., Nair, U. S. & Niyogi, D. Urban Modification of Convection and Rainfall in Complex
800 Terrain. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **45**, 2507–2515 (2018).
- 801 34. Sátyro, Z. C., Farias, C., Candido, L. A. & Veiga, J. A. Urban sprawl can inhibit convection and
802 decrease rainfall over an Amazonian city during a squall line type phenomenon. *Urban Clim.* **40**,
803 101023 (2021).
- 804 35. Best, M. J. & Grimmond, C. S. B. Key Conclusions of the First International Urban Land Surface
805 Model Comparison Project. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **96**, 805–819 (2015).
- 806 36. Grimmond, C. S. B. *et al.* The International Urban Energy Balance Models Comparison Project:
807 First Results from Phase 1. *J. Appl. Meteorol. Climatol.* **49**, 1268–1292 (2010).
- 808 37. Grimmond, C. S. B. *et al.* Initial results from Phase 2 of the international urban energy balance
809 model comparison. *Int. J. Climatol.* **31**, 244–272 (2011).
- 810 38. Jongen, H. J. *et al.* The Water Balance Representation in Urban-PLUMBER Land Surface
811 Models. *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.* **16**, e2024MS004231 (2024).
- 812 39. Lipson, M. J. *et al.* Evaluation of 30 urban land surface models in the Urban-PLUMBER project:
813 Phase 1 results. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **150**, 126–169 (2024).
- 814 40. Lean, H. W. *et al.* The hectometric modelling challenge: Gaps in the current state of the art and
815 ways forward towards the implementation of 100-m scale weather and climate models. *Q. J. R.*
816 *Meteorol. Soc.* **150**, 4671–4708 (2024).

- 817 41. Zhao, L. *et al.* Global multi-model projections of local urban climates. *Nat. Clim. Change* **11**, 152–
818 157 (2021).
- 819 42. Ching, J. *et al.* WUDAPT: An Urban Weather, Climate, and Environmental Modeling Infrastructure
820 for the Anthropocene. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **99**, 1907–1924 (2018).
- 821 43. Demuzere, M., Argüeso, D., Zonato, A. & Kittner, J. W2W: A Python package that injects
822 WUDAPT's Local Climate Zone information in WRF. *J. Open Source Softw.* **7**, 4432 (2022).
- 823 44. Demuzere, M., He, C., Martilli, A. & Zonato, A. Technical documentation for the hybrid 100-m
824 global land cover dataset with Local Climate Zones for WRF. (2023)
825 doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7670792.
- 826 45. Campanale, A., Adinolfi, M., Raffa, M., Schulz, J.-P. & Mercogliano, P. Investigating urban heat
827 islands over Rome and Milan during a summer period through the TERRA_URB parameterization
828 in the ICON model. *Urban Clim.* **60**, 102335 (2025).
- 829 46. Canton, J. & Dipankar, A. Climatological analysis of urban heat island effects in Swiss cities. *Int.*
830 *J. Climatol.* **44**, 1549–1565 (2024).
- 831 47. Cui, F. *et al.* Interactions between the summer urban heat islands and heat waves in Beijing
832 during 2000–2018. *Atmospheric Res.* **291**, 106813 (2023).
- 833 48. Kamath, H. G. *et al.* GLOBal Building heights for Urban Studies (UT-GLOBUS) for city- and
834 street- scale urban simulations: Development and first applications. *Sci. Data* **11**, 886 (2024).
- 835 49. Cheng, Y. *et al.* U-Surf: A Global 1 km spatially continuous urban surface property dataset for
836 kilometer-scale urban-resolving Earth system modeling. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* 1–38
837 (2024) doi:10.5194/essd-2024-416.
- 838 50. Liao, W. *et al.* GloUCP: a global 1 km spatially continuous urban canopy parameters for the WRF
839 model. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **17**, 2535–2551 (2025).
- 840 51. Riahi, K. *et al.* RCP 8.5—A scenario of comparatively high greenhouse gas emissions. *Clim.*
841 *Change* **109**, 33–57 (2011).
- 842 52. Giorgi, F., Coppola, E., Teichmann, C. & Jacob, D. Editorial for the CORDEX-CORE Experiment I
843 Special Issue. *Clim. Dyn.* **57**, 1265–1268 (2021).
- 844 53. Remedio, A. R. *et al.* Evaluation of New CORDEX Simulations Using an Updated Köppen–
845 Trewartha Climate Classification. *Atmosphere* **10**, 726 (2019).
- 846 54. Teichmann, C. *et al.* Assessing mean climate change signals in the global CORDEX-CORE
847 ensemble. *Clim. Dyn.* **57**, 1269–1292 (2021).
- 848 55. Jackson, T. L., Feddema, J. J., Oleson, K. W., Bonan, G. B. & Bauer, J. T. Parameterization of
849 Urban Characteristics for Global Climate Modeling. *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.* **100**, 848–865
850 (2010).
- 851 56. Kotlarski, S. A subgrid glacier parameterisation for use in regional climate modelling. (University
852 of Hamburg Hamburg, 2007). doi:10.17617/2.994357.
- 853 57. Semmler, T., Jacob, D., Schlünzen, K. H. & Podzun, R. Influence of Sea Ice Treatment in a
854 Regional Climate Model on Boundary Layer Values in the Fram Strait Region. *Mon. Weather*
855 *Rev.* **132**, 985–999 (2004).
- 856 58. Hagemann, S. *An Improved Land Surface Parameter Dataset for Global and Regional Climate*
857 *Models*. 21 https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_2344576_7/component/file_3192501/content
858 (2002).
- 859 59. Hagemann, S., Botzet, M., Dümenil, L. & Machehauer, B. *Derivation of Global GCM Boundary*
860 *Conditions from 1 Km Land Use Satellite Data*. [https://hdl.handle.net/21.11116/0000-0001-2C5E-](https://hdl.handle.net/21.11116/0000-0001-2C5E-6)
861 **6** (1999).
- 862 60. Eidenshink, J. C. & Faundeen, J. L. The 1 km AVHRR global land data set: first stages in
863 implementation. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* **15**, 3443–3462 (1994).
- 864 61. USGS. USGS EROS Archive - Land Cover Products - Global Land Cover Characterization
865 (GLCC). (2002).
- 866 62. Pietikäinen, J.-P. *et al.* REMO2020: a modernized modular regional climate model. *EGUsphere*
867 1–57 (2025) doi:10.5194/egusphere-2025-1586.
- 868 63. Brousse, O., Martilli, A., Foley, M., Mills, G. & Bechtel, B. WUDAPT, an efficient land use

- 869 producing data tool for mesoscale models? Integration of urban LCZ in WRF over Madrid. *Urban*
870 *Clim.* **17**, 116–134 (2016).
- 871 64. Varentsov, M., Fenner, D., Meier, F., Samsonov, T. & Demuzere, M. Quantifying Local and
872 Mesoscale Drivers of the Urban Heat Island of Moscow with Reference and Crowdsourced
873 Observations. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **9**, 716968 (2021).
- 874 65. Li, C., Zhang, N., Wang, Y. & Chen, Y. Modeling Urban Heat Islands and Thermal Comfort During
875 a Heat Wave Event in East China With CLM5 Incorporating Local Climate Zones. *J. Geophys.*
876 *Res. Atmospheres* **128**, e2023JD038883 (2023).
- 877 66. Stewart, I. D. & Oke, T. R. Local Climate Zones for Urban Temperature Studies. *Bull. Am.*
878 *Meteorol. Soc.* **93**, 1879–1900 (2012).
- 879 67. Diez-Sierra, J. *et al.* The Worldwide C3S CORDEX Grand Ensemble: A Major Contribution to
880 Assess Regional Climate Change in the IPCC AR6 Atlas. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **103**, E2804–
881 E2826 (2022).
- 882 68. Melchiorri, M. *et al.* *Stats in the City: The GHSL Urban Centre Database 2025 : Public Release*
883 *GHS UCDB R2024*. (Publications Office of the European Union, 2024).
- 884 69. Chakraborty, T. & Lee, X. A simplified urban-extent algorithm to characterize surface urban heat
885 islands on a global scale and examine vegetation control on their spatiotemporal variability. *Int. J.*
886 *Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinformation* **74**, 269–280 (2019).
- 887 70. Peng, S. *et al.* Surface Urban Heat Island Across 419 Global Big Cities. *Environ. Sci. Technol.*
888 **46**, 696–703 (2012).
- 889 71. Rozenfeld, H. D. *et al.* Laws of population growth. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **105**, 18702–
890 18707 (2008).
- 891 72. Sismanidis, P., Bechtel, B., Perry, M. & Ghent, D. The Seasonality of Surface Urban Heat Islands
892 across Climates. *Remote Sens.* **14**, 2318 (2022).
- 893 73. Venter, Z. S., Chakraborty, T. & Lee, X. Crowdsourced air temperatures contrast satellite
894 measures of the urban heat island and its mechanisms. *Sci. Adv.* **7**, eabb9569 (2021).
- 895 74. Zhou, B., Rybski, D. & Kropp, J. P. On the statistics of urban heat island intensity. *Geophys. Res.*
896 *Lett.* **40**, 5486–5491 (2013).
- 897 75. Diez-Sierra, J. *et al.* Delineating CORDEX model urban areas and their rural surroundings for
898 megacities worldwide to assess urban climate change. *Sci. Data* **submitted**, (2025).
- 899 76. Shastri, H., Barik, B., Ghosh, S., Venkataraman, C. & Sadavarte, P. Flip flop of Day-night and
900 Summer-Winter Surface Urban Heat Island Intensity in India. *Sci. Rep.* **7**, 40178 (2017).
- 901 77. Menne, M. J., Durre, I., Vose, R. S., Gleason, B. E. & Houston, T. G. An Overview of the Global
902 Historical Climatology Network-Daily Database. *J. Atmospheric Ocean. Technol.* **29**, 897–910
903 (2012).
- 904

905

906